

Spectrophotometric Study of Iron (III) Glycolate Complex

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The stoichiometry of the complex iron (III)-glycolate complex in the pH range 2.5—4.0 has been investigated. The complex contains iron (III) and glycollic acid in the ratio 1 : 2. The complex has a maximum absorption at 360 nm and the dissociation constant $(1.04-1.40) \times 10^{-8}$. The free energy of complex formation has been found to be—1083 cal/mole.

Fe(III)—lactate complex have been studied by Bakore and Bhardwaj¹ and have reported 1 : 2 iron-lactic acid complex. No report seems to be available on the spectrophotometric studies of Iron (III)-Glycollic acid complex, hence the present investigation was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Glycollic acid (Light & Co.) was used. Ferric Ammonium Sulphate and Sodium hydroxide used were of B.D.H. "AnalaR" specifications. All other reagents used were chemically pure.

pH of the solutions were measured with a Atomic Energy manufactured pH meter. The spectrophotometric measurements were carried out with a Hilger U.V. Speck spectrophotometer using cells of a path length of 10 mm at $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$.

RESULTS

Spectral characteristics of the complex; Mixtures containing various proportions of iron (III)-glycollic acid, glycollic acid being always in excess were prepared.

Absorbance of solutions at different wavelengths was measured in each case. In all cases the maximum absorption occurred at 360 nm. Further under these conditions the Beer's law has been found to be valid (cf. fig. 4). The absorbance of solutions at 360 nm is not sensibly affected by changes in pH in the range pH : 2.5—4.0.

Stoichiometry of the Complex : Job's method of continuous variation² as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper³ and also the mole ratio method was used to determine the stoichiometry of the complex.

Job's Method : Absorption measurements were made with a large number of equimolecular and non-equimolecular solutions at 360, 385 nm. A typical set of data is shown in fig. 1 (cf. fig. 1).

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For both the wavelengths the maximum absorption was observed when the mole fraction of iron(III) in the solution was 1/3. This shows that the ratio of iron(III) : glycollic acid in the complex is 1 : 2.

Mole Ratio Method : The stoichiometry of the complex and the dissociation constant of the complex was also determined by the mole ratio method as proposed by Yoe and Jones⁴. A typical of the data of the mole ratio method are shown in Fig. 2. Fig. 2 gives a plot of absorbance against $[GA]/[Fe(III)]$. The sharp break appears at $[GA]/[Fe(III)] = 2$ which confirms that the ratio of Fe(III) to glycollic acid in the complex is 1 : 2.

The dissociation constant of the complex is calculated by the mole ratio method according to the following equation :

C is the total concentration of the complex in moles per litre assuming no dissociation and α is the degree of dissociation. The equilibrium constant K is given by

$$K = \frac{[Fe(III)][L]^2}{[Fe^{+3}L_2]}$$

$$K = \frac{\alpha C \times (2\alpha C)^2}{C \times (1-\alpha)}$$

α may be obtained from the mole ratio curves by the following relationship :

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_g}{E_m}$$

where E_m is the maximum extinction obtained from the horizontal portion of the curve, indicating that the whole of the metal ion is present in the form of a complex, E_s is the extinction at the stoichiometric molar ratio of the ligand to the metal in the complex. The value of K has been calculated to be equal to 1.4×10^{-8} .

Calculation of the dissociation constant by slope ratio method: A series of solutions containing a known excess of Fe(III) i.e. $[Fe(III)] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$ and varying proportions of glycollic acid were prepared. In all the cases $[Fe(III)] \gg [GA]$. The absorbance of these solutions measured at $360 m\mu$ are recorded below in Table 1.

TABLE 1

$[Fe(III)] = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $pH = 2.5-4.$, Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$

$[GA] \times 10^3 M$	Absorbance	$(A - A_0)$
0.0	0.280	—
2.5	0.301	.021
5.0	0.315	.035
7.5	0.330	.050
10.0	0.344	.064
12.5	0.359	.079
15.0	0.372	.092
17.5	0.388	.108
20.0	0.403	.123

The complex formation reaction is expressed as

The dissociation constant of the complex C is then expressed as

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe(III)}][\text{HL}]^2}{[\text{Fe(III)L}_2]} = \frac{[\text{Fe(III)}]\{[\text{L}] - 2[\text{C}]\}}{[\text{C}]} \quad (1)$$

where $[\text{Fe(III)}]$ and $[\text{L}]$ are the initial concentrations of iron(III) and glycollic acid respectively. C is the concentration of the complex and K is the dissociation constant of the complex.

Eqn. (1) can be rearranged as

$$[\text{C}] = [\text{L}] - \frac{[\text{L}]^2}{4[\text{C}]} + \frac{K}{4[\text{Fe(III)}]} \quad (2)$$

since $[\text{Fe(III)}] \gg [\text{L}]$, we have $[\text{C}] = [\text{L}]/2$, so the equation (2) reduces to

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{[\text{L}]}{2} + \frac{K}{4[\text{Fe(III)}]} \quad (3)$$

The concentration of the complex C is related to the absorbance by

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{A - A^0}{E_c} \quad (4)$$

where A^0 is the absorbance of Fe(III) solution in the absence of glycollic acid and E_c is the extinction coefficient of the complex. Combining (3) and (4) we get

$$(A - A^0) = \frac{E_c[\text{L}]}{2} + \frac{E_c K}{4[\text{Fe(III)}]} \quad (5)$$

From equation (5) it is evident that a plot of $A - A^0$ against $[\text{L}]$ should be a straight line with slope = $\frac{E_c}{2}$ and intercept = $\frac{E_c K}{4[\text{Fe(III)}]}$

Fig. 3 shows the plot of $A - A^0$ against $[\text{L}]$. This plot is linear in conformity with equation (5) and permits calculation of extinction coefficient of the complex and its dissociation constant K [stability constant $K^* = 1/K$]. Calculations show that the values of E_c and K are 1160 and 1.04×10^{-8} , respectively.

In another series of solutions the concentration of glycollic acid was kept constant at $5 \times 10^{-4}M$ and that of iron (III) varied, such that $[\text{L}] \gg [\text{Fe(III)}]$. The absorbance of these solutions at 360 $m\mu$ are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2

[GA] = $5 \times 10^{-4} M$. pH = 2.5-4. Temp. = $25^\circ \pm 1^\circ$

[Fe(III)] $\times 10^5$ moles litre ⁻¹	Absorbance at 360 m μ
0.00	0.000
1.25	0.014
2.50	0.028
3.75	0.041
5.00	0.055
6.25	0.069
7.50	0.082
8.75	0.097

When glycollic acid is in excess the dissociation constant K can be written as

$$K = \frac{[\text{Fe(III)}] - [\text{C}][\text{L}]^2}{[\text{C}]}$$

which on rearrangement can be written as

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{[\text{L}]^2}{K + [\text{L}]^2} \times [\text{Fe(III)}] \quad (6)$$

The concentration of the complex is related to the absorbance by

$$\frac{A}{E_c} = [\text{C}] \quad (7)$$

Combining (6) and (7)

$$A = \frac{E_c [L]^2}{K + [L]^2} [\text{Fe(III)}] \quad (8)$$

Thus a plot of A against the concentration of iron(III) should be a straight line passing through origin and this is so in fig. 4. The slope of the straight line gives the value of $\frac{E_c [L]^2}{K + [L]^2}$. The slope of the straight line has a value of 1160. Thus using $E_c = 1160$ from the earlier experiment and $[L] = 5 \times 10^{-4} M$ the value of K has been calculated to be equal to $K = 1.36 \times 10^{-8}$.

This method thus not only proves the stoichiometry of the complex but also enables one to calculate the dissociation constant of the complex.

The free energy of complex formation has been evaluated at 25° by using the average value of K as 1.26×10^{-8} by the relationship :

$$\Delta F = -RT \ln K^*$$

$$\Delta F = -10834. \text{ cal/mole}$$

* K is stability constant of the complex and is inverse of dissociation constant.

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